

DEVELOPMENT OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF TEACHING SPEECH ETIQUETTE

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Annotation: In the teacher's pedagogical skill, his speech and oratorical skills are of great importance. Therefore, the deeper the teacher knows the language and the more vocabulary he has, the richer his thinking will be. The word is the foundation of all arguments, all thoughts, the foundation of the teacher's speech. **Keywords:** communicative competence, speech behavior, communication, interaction, dialogue, art of oratory, correctness of speech, accuracy of speech, logic of speech, conversational method, speech etiquette, monologic speech, dialogical speech.

In the modern educational space, when teaching foreign students, the Russian language, the formation of their communicative competence is of particular importance. This term was first introduced into science by the American ethnopsychologist Dell Hymes, who connected linguistic competence with the possibilities of its social application in a variety of situations and realities of life. The scientist defined communicative competence as follows: "knowledge of a language, which is understood not only as possession of grammatical and vocabulary levels, but also as the ability to choose options due to situational, social or other extralinguistic factors" In domestic science, the term "communicative competence" was introduced. He proposed to understand communicative competence as "... the choice and implementation of speech behavior programs depending on a person's ability to navigate in a particular communication environment; the ability to classify situations depending on the topic, tasks, communicative attitudes that arise in students before the conversation, as well as during the conversation in the process of mutual adaptation " Researcher M. Z. Biboletova proposes to single out the following components of communicative competence: 1. speech (communicative) competence - the development of communication skills in four main types of speech activity (speaking, listening, reading, writing); 2. language competence - mastering new language means (phonetic, spelling, lexical, grammatical) in accordance with the topics and situations of communication, mastering knowledge of language phenomena of the language being studied, different ways

of expressing thoughts in the language; 3. sociocultural / intercultural competence - familiarization with the culture, traditions, realities of the country of the language being studied within the framework of topics, areas and situations of communication; 4. compensatory competence - the development of skills to get out of the situation in the face of a lack of language means in receiving and transmitting information". An analysis of scientific papers on communicative competence proves that it is a field of knowledge that consists of combining various disciplines: philosophy, linguistics, psycholinguistics, psychology, pedagogy, rhetoric, speech etiquette, linguistic and cultural studies, sociology. Therefore, the communicative competencies that students receive in classes in Russian as a foreign language necessarily include not only the study of theoretical linguistic material, but also the mastery of certain linguistic and cultural knowledge, culture and tactics of communication, speech etiquette. Students gain experience of working in a team, in the process of which they develop their own life position, research and creative opportunities. Communication acts in this situation as a factor that serves to educate the personality, the formation of its worldview and attitude. The organization of teaching the Russian language in the process of communication reveals the unique possibilities of the communicative method, the basis of which is the teaching of foreign students through their communication. In order to successfully carry out pedagogical activities, the teacher's speech must meet certain requirements, that is, it must meet the communicative qualities necessary for the formation of public speaking skills, and his speech must correspond to several literary norms: that is, modern norms, expressive, to the norms of the literary language. Speech culture is necessary for written and oral form. Attention to speech culture is one of the human qualities that every citizen is required to consciously acquire, not only from teachers. The development of speaking ability depends only on the enthusiasm of the teacher. Thanks to this ability, the speech culture of the teacher is formed. When the teacher's speech is said, oral and written speech is meant. Teachers correct and correct their shortcomings when necessary on the basis of oral speech. The speech of a teacher with technical speaking experience should ensure the following:

Communication between the teacher and his students. interaction and productive communication: full acceptance, understanding and strengthening of knowledge in the educational process. To have a positive effect on the activity of students, on their minds and emotions in order to form the instinct of ability and talent in them; Social perceptive ability- social imagination ability, ability to control oneself organization of educational and practical activities of students

according to the purpose Another main feature of the teacher's oral speech is that it is improvisational (without any preparation). In order for communicative speech to be successful, teachers need to develop a number of special skills specific to the art of public speaking. The ability to control one's mental state in communication. The ability to exert voluntary influence and persuasiveness. Analyzing communication as a special type of communicative activity, which has its own purpose, structure, processes, ways of implementing the tasks and the final result, one can judge the methodological basis of teaching communication. For foreign students studying Russian in groups, this is especially true, since communication in such a situation is “ a complex speech-creative skill that allows a person to achieve results in dialogue and interaction, correctly build and understand various texts, adequately use language and speech means in relation to specific conditions and tasks of communication”. Modern life in a multicultural, multilingual society that unites people with different mentalities, traditions, religions and upbringing should offer young people to learn how to use such intercultural competencies that will be implemented in the ability to respect other cultures, habits and upbringing, to perceive the point of view of other people, realizing that the process of communication is always two-way. And the communicative competencies associated with the student's oral communication, the ability to express one's own opinion clearly and clearly, enter into a dialogue, understand the information addressed to him and adequately respond to it, have not only a linguistic and speech-creative, but also a very important psychological context. Indeed, the basis of communicative competence is not only natural sociability, communication skills, but also the characteristics of the individual himself, expressed in the trinity of his emotions, thoughts and actions implemented in a certain team, in a specific social situation. The communicative competence of foreign students can be developed, deepened, enriched, on the one hand, by acquiring new knowledge, assimilation of information, gaining skills and experience; and on the other hand - correcting their own mistakes, changing the usual, established forms and clichés. This once again emphasizes the close connection between the development of communicative competence - the goal of teaching Russian to foreign students - with the organization of interpersonal communication in the classroom, which is so necessary to achieve this goal. After all, it is thanks to him that a foreign student who has come for an internship feels more secure and calm in a strange, unusual social environment. Communication in RFL classes can be considered as two types of special communicative activity: separately between students and between students and a teacher.

Both of them have a serious theoretical and methodological basis, goals, objectives, structure, operations, methods and means of implementation, and most importantly - the end result, when students develop speech-creative skills that will help them succeed in interacting with other people, they will teach them to correctly understand others and compose their own texts, adequately using language and speech capabilities.

At the same time, students develop their own experience in solving various communicative problems, putting their knowledge and skills into practice in various situations, the ability to direct and regulate the communicative process in relation to specific communication conditions. "The development of competence in communication is associated with a focus on acquiring a rich, diverse palette of psychological positions, means that help the completeness of self-expression (self-presentation) of partners, all facets of their adequacy - perceptual, communicative, interactive". The development and improvement of communication skills between students and between students and the teacher is a constant creative work, training the ability to see oneself from the outside. The position of mutual interest, openness, the ability to empathize and sympathize are of particular importance when students from different countries, different ages, different levels of Russian language proficiency study in the same group. In this case, serious attention should be paid to the peculiarities of cultural interaction, norms and rules of behavior, speech etiquette, for example: how to look at a communication partner, how to listen to him, how to thank, how to object, how to express your own opinion, different from the opinion of the interlocutor, what it is necessary to say and do to cheer up, praise the partner. In classes in Russian as a foreign language, it is necessary to make the most of the main functions of communication:

1. Communicative functions. With their help, in the process of communication, the interconnection of students at the level of group interaction is carried out. Students talk to each other, share information they have, read and compose texts, use Internet materials, use naturally expressive means person (intonation, tone of voice, facial expressions, pantomime, various subject actions, etc.).
2. Informative functions. They are carried out in the process of group communication in unity with communicative tasks. There is a transfer of new information from one communication partner to another in the form of various kinds of messages in the form of knowledge, practical experience, expressive behavior of interlocutors.
3. Cognitive functions. In the process of communication, foreign students perceive the information received from the teacher and learning partners from

texts, Internet sources, personal experience, national culture, etc. Then comes the comprehension of the perceived meanings with the help of thinking, awareness, representation, imagination and fantasy. Their combination and the interaction of communicative, informative and cognitive functions affect the success of foreign students in mastering knowledge and the formation of their competencies in the field of language and speech.

4. Emotive functions. In the process of communication, students have feelings, emotions, experiences, sometimes even passion. It is important for the teacher to organize the process of teaching foreign students in such a way that they are interested in the lesson, their emotions are positive, and the perception of information would be aesthetic in nature and have a positive impact on students. Then it will be easier, more pleasant and more interesting for them to study. It is important that the children feel comfortable in class, they feel calm, not shy, not afraid to make any mistake, to look ridiculous.

5. Conative functions. Conative functions express human desires, aspirations and motive forces, regulating the behavior and interaction of communication partners in the aspect of coordinating and coordinating their joint activities. This process is realized through the exchange of thoughts, feelings, relationships, individual views and positions.

6. Creative features. The task of the creative functions of communication is the transformation of students, changing their axiological attitudes towards obtaining and assimilating new information, new knowledge, educating the personality, psycholinguistic mutual influence of communication partners. Oratory is the oral form of speech.

Oratory is the art of speaking. Speech culture is a concept that applies to both oral and written forms of speech. If we talk about the main features of the speech, they are the following: The correctness and fluency of the speech is its correspondence to the norms of the literary language. In this case, attention is paid to two aspects: 1) emphasis, 2) adherence to grammatical norms. Clarity and effectiveness of speech is a factor affecting the audience of a meaningful speech. The teacher gives knowledge to students based on clear facts with the fluency of words and language, the ability to speak, and develops their skills and abilities. It is necessary for the teacher to be clear in his speech and to feel his responsibility deeply. Accuracy is the fact that the subject being studied corresponds to the reality expressed by the teacher. The logicity of the speech depends on the logicity of the speech, first of all, the teacher's vocabulary, ability to think, perception skills. The teacher knows the language very well and can have a wide vocabulary. But if he does not have deep knowledge of the topic

he is thinking about, if he cannot analyze the knowledge within his thinking, the art of speaking will not be effective. The purity and expressiveness of the speech - the purity of the teacher's speech is determined first of all by its expression in accordance with the norms of the literary language. Teachers' beautiful and content-rich speech is evaluated depending on whether it is structured in accordance with the requirements of the current rich Uzbek language. Dialectism and barbarism destroy the purity of speech. The purity of the speech is that it is free from various dialect words and is expressed only in literary language. Language tools are used according to the situation, without tight words and phrases, the teacher's speech is natural and sincere, the listener and the reader attracts students quickly. The teacher attracts the attention of the students with the perfection, purity, and impressiveness of the speech, finds a way to their hearts, eliminates all the conflicts encountered in the professional pedagogical activity without any difficulties. As a result, the teacher never gets tired of his pedagogical activities and continues to educate the next generation. By means of influence, the personality of students develops, the efficiency of mastering knowledge increases due to interest, curiosity, strengthening the motivation for obtaining new information, self-initiated study of the material is stimulated, and there is an increase in the creative activity of children. Group classes in Russian as a foreign language, conducted in the form of interactive learning, allow you to simultaneously solve several important tasks: cognitive, related to the study of a specific language topic in a specific learning situation; communicative-developing, the task of which is to develop basic communication skills within the study group and outside it in various communicative situations; socially oriented, helping foreign students to adapt in a strange, unfamiliar, unusual community for them. And if earlier in the educational process communication was considered mainly as a means of educating the individual, then in the modern pedagogical space, in connection with the changed requirements and tasks of education, communication in every possible way contributes to the educational process, deepening and developing it, reveals the potential resources of education, helps students to realize their needs and opportunities, contributes to their personal growth and creative activity. The main content of the personal component of a person is the mood for dialogue. It is important for a Russian as a foreign language teacher to teach students not only to speak Russian correctly, but also to communicate, to be able to overcome certain communicative, psychological and behavioral difficulties, to correct their own speech experience, possible dissatisfaction and tension that arises in the process of communication, to establish interaction, the main content of which is

mutual learning, learning new things, exchanging information and establishing interaction that is favorable for the development of speech communication of foreign students.

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